

6407 Miles Away

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If I could reach you, you know I would.
If I could touch you, I wish I could.
If I had one wish, I would want it to be you wishing for me
Yes, you are miles away, 6,407 miles away from me.

If only I could hold you,
And inside your dreams, make them all come true,
I would hold you so tight.
But I know it is impossible to do;
It's like chasing rainbows across the sky.

If only you could fall asleep next to me,
I could watch your charming face the entire night,
Counting your breaths until you wake up.
But that cannot happen right now,
Because we are 6,407 miles apart.

Yet know that though we are miles apart,
It is a wonderful blessing that you simply exist.
It is good to be with you in this special space,
Despite the distance, despite the time.

Loving you is incredibly beautiful,
And I could live the next one hundred years, though 6,407 miles apart,
Because I hold you safely in my heart
So, I put my heart right into your hand.

The day will come when you hold me in your arms,
Putting an end to the distance we always have to fight.
We don't know what comes next, so let us keep each other;
Let us stay together to see the end of these 6,407 miles apart.

DOI 10.5281/zenodo.20605601

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